

A STUDY ON ATTITUDE TOWARDS PRACTICE IN TEACHING AND TEACHING PERFORMANCE OF PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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ABSTRACT

Practice in Teaching is one of the important components of Teacher Education Programme. A good teaching practice of Pre-service Teachers is an indicator towards future success in the teaching profession. During the process of practice teaching, Pre-service Teachers gain an awareness of their teaching by seeking feedback from mentors, supervisors, teacher educators, peers and through their self-reflection. Overall Practice Teaching experience provides strong insight for their improvement in Teaching Performance. Several factors may contribute to the success of Practice Teaching including teaching aptitude, attitude and achievement level and so on. The present study attempts to investigate the Attitude of Pre-service Teachers towards their Practice in Teaching experience and its relation between Teaching Performance. The study utilized a descriptive survey method which involved a sample of 50 Pre-service Teachers. The data on Teaching Performance was collected using ‘Assessment Scale for Teaching Performance’ developed by St. Ann’s College of Education (Autonomous) Mangaluru. Attitude of Pre-service Teachers towards Practice in Teaching was collected after their practice teaching experience by administering a standardized tool on “Teaching Practice Exercise and Teachers’ Professional Development (TPETPD) developed by the Oparah, Nwoke, & Eucharia (2017). Data was analysed using inferential statistic ‘t’ and Product Moment Correlation ‘r’ at 0.05 level of significance. Results of the study indicated no significant difference among Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers’ Attitude towards Practice in Teaching and Teaching Performance. Significant positive relationship was also observed in the Attitude of Pre-service Teachers towards Practice in Teaching and Teaching Performance.

Key Words: Attitude towards Practice in Teaching, Teaching Performance, Pre-service Teachers

Introduction

Traditionally the teacher was concerned with passing on the knowledge to the students. But the role of the present-day teacher has become complex, very challenging and multifaceted on

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account of changes occurring in the content areas of all disciplines. Teachers are expected to create new knowledge, introduce it to the students and thereby bring desirable changes in the learner. Preparing one for the teaching profession is an arduous task. Teacher Education Institutions play a vital role in developing the skills and professional competencies of novice teachers in the making. The Practice in Teaching is one of the most significant parts of teacher education programme. It encompasses teaching skills, sound pedagogical theory and professional skills. Practice teaching provides an opportunity to put theories into practice and develop deeper understanding of educational principles and their implications of learning.

Practice Teaching is considered the pivotal component of Teacher Education programme. It aims at placing the trainees in a position where they learn to use their theoretical knowledge effectively and in a confident manner, for communicating the contents of their subjects in classroom situation as well as in a curricular activity in an outside the classroom situations. During this period the student teachers get actively engaged in extensive direct experience in a school under the guidance of the staff of teacher’s college and the cooperating school to learn the dimensions of the profession of teaching and to acquire competencies required for entering the teaching profession. Practice Teaching also provides the best situation for assessing the mastery of knowledge and skills required for an effective teacher. Thus, we can call it as a ‘key-phase’ of the total teacher education programme (Mangala, 2010).

Rationale for the Study

It has been rightly said that teacher education should be the joint responsibility of training colleges and schools where practice teaching is done. Practice in Teaching is accepted as a very vital experience for teachers-in-making by all the teacher education institutions. In order to prepare Pre-service Teachers for Practice Teaching, teacher education institutes provides pre-teaching experience along with demonstration and criticism lessons and helps them to induce teaching skills. Overall Practice in Teaching aims at providing actual classroom experience and improves their skills in teaching before they become teachers at schools. Therefore pre-service teacher education programme must give extreme importance for developing positive attitude among Pre-service Teachers towards practice teaching and thereby enhancing their Teaching Performance. Literature reviewed in the current field helped the investigator to strengthen the rationale for the present study. Oparah, Nwoke, & Eucharia, (2017) conducted a study on Influence of Teaching

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Practice Exercise on Pre-service Teachers’ Professional Development. The result of the study revealed that teaching practice is very essential in pre-service teachers’ professional development irrespective of gender. The study recommended that pre-service teachers should take their teaching practice exercise serious to enable them function properly during their teaching profession. The study conducted by Meutia, Elyza, & Yusnila, (2018) investigated the pre-service teachers’ performance in the Field Experience Program after taking a microteaching class. The results of the study indicated the pre-service teachers improved their classroom teaching performance during their Field Experience Program. The study Marasigan, (2018) investigated the teaching performance of pre-service teachers as assessed by the student-teachers themselves and their cooperating teacher. The results of the study showed that teaching performance of pre-service teachers as very satisfactory in terms of mastery of the subject matter and facilitating learning. Based on the findings, the study suggested recommendation for the improvement of teaching performance. The study (Paghasian, 2017) investigated the Pre-service-Teacher Education (PTE) in terms of personal preparation, professional preparation and classroom management and Practice-Teaching Performances (PTP). Results revealed that PTE teachers have an appreciable performance in terms of personal -professional preparation, classroom management and average in practice teaching.

Studies revealed that Teaching Performance during Practice in Teaching is one of the essential indicators for the professional growth of Pre-service Teachers. Inorder to improve their own Teaching Performance, Pre-service teachers are generally expected to be aware of their own teaching practices such as their abilities, methods and techniques, communication skills, assessment techniques, and the strenghts and weakness of their teaching focusing on entire teaching learning process. This will help them to develop positive attitude towards Practice Teaching and enhance their Teaching Performance. Therefore, in the present study investigator made an attempt to study the Attitude of Pre-service Teachers regarding their Practice Teaching expereince and its realtionship with their Teaching Performance.

Statement of Problem

A study on Attitude towards Practice in Teaching and Teaching Performance among Pre-service Teachers of Secondary School Level of Dakshina Kannada District.

Operational Definitions of the Term

Teaching Performance of Pre-service Teachers

Teachers’ Performance is the ability of the teacher to impart the relevant skills, knowledge using appropriate methods consistently over time to enhance students’ learning and achievements. It denotes teachers’ ability to functions effectively in performing his teaching tasks with high skills and effort with regards to his subject matter using a sound pedagogical content that leads to student’s understanding and effective learning (Bashir, Alias, Saleh, & Halizah,2017)

In the present study Teaching Performance refers to the different teaching skills exhibited by the Pre-service Teachers during their Practice in Teaching session. It was assessed by the teacher educators using the ‘Assessment Scale on Teacher Performance’ constructed by St. Ann’s College of Education (Autonomous) Mangaluru based on lesson plan writing, content competency, transaction of content, effective classroom management, communication and competencies in core teaching skills.

Attitude towards Practice in Teaching

Attitude is an important attribute towards any profession. Maliki (2013) opined that individual’s attitudes toward their profession influence their performance and it affects their competence and achievement. The belief someone has about any job determined the success of that person in the profession (Ikitde & Ado, 2015).

In the present study Attitude towards Practice in Teaching refers to the Preservice Teachers beliefs about their teaching performance during Practice in Teaching. It was assessed by using a standardized tool on “Teaching Practice Exercise and Teachers’ Professional Development (TPETPD) developed by the Oparah, Nwoke, & Eucharia (2017).

Pre-service Teachers

Pre-service Teachers are the prospective teachers who undergo formal education and training and gradually introduced to the teaching profession in order to become an effective and efficient teacher. In the present study Pre-service Teachers refers to the student teachers of Secondary School Level pursuing Two-year B.Ed. Degree of the year 2017-2019 under Mangalore University.

Objectives of the Study

- To find the deference between Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers’ Attitude towards

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Practice in Teaching

- To find the deference between Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers’ Teaching Performance
- To study the relationship between Pre-service Teachers Attitude towards Practice in Teaching and Teaching Performance

Hypotheses of the Study

- Ho1: There is no significant difference between Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers’ Attitude towards Practice in Teaching
- Ho2: There is no significant difference between Arts and Science Pre-service Teacher’s Teaching Performance
- Ho 3: There is no significant relationship between Pre-service Teacher’s Attitude towards Practice in Teaching and Teaching Performance

Methodology

The present study utilized descriptive survey method. All the Pre-service Teachers pursuing two-year B.Ed. degree course under Mangalore University of the academic year 2017-19 were the population of the study. Sample consisted of randomly selected 50 Pre-service Teachers. Attitude towards Practice Teaching was measured using a standardized tool constructed by Oparah, Nwoke & Ikwuanusi (2017) on ‘Teaching Practice Exercise and Teachers Professional Development (TPETPD)’. Teaching Performance of the pre-service teachers was measured using ‘Assessment Scale for Teacher Performance’ developed by St. Ann’s College of Education (Autonomous), Mangaluru. Hypotheses were tested using ‘t’ test and Pearson Product Moment Correlation ‘r’ at 0.05 level of significance.

Analysis and Interpretation of the Data

Objective One: To find the deference between Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers’ Attitude towards Practice in Teaching

Ho1: There is no significant difference between Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers’ Attitude towards Practice in Teaching

‘t’ was employed to test the hypothesis and the level of significance was fixed at 0.05. The details of the test are given in the Table 1

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Table 1: Summary of ‘t’ Test Analysis

Attitude towards Practice Teaching	N	Mean	SD	df	‘t’ value	Result
Arts	30	51.4	5.58	48	0.57	Not significant at 0.05 level
Science	20	50.5	4.53			

From the Table 1, it is observed that the obtained ‘t’ value 0.57 is lesser than the table value 2.01 at 0.05 level of significance with df 48. Hence the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference between Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers Attitude towards Practice in Teaching” is accepted. This implies that both Arts and Science Pre-service teachers have similar Attitude towards Practice in Teaching.

Objective Two: To find the deference between Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers’ Teaching Performance.

Ho2: There is no significant difference between Arts and Science Pre-service Teacher’s Teaching Performance.

‘t’ was employed to test the hypothesis and the level of significance was fixed at 0.05. The details of the test are given in the Table 2

Table 2: Summary of ‘t’ Test Analysis

Teaching Performance	N	Mean	SD	df	‘t’ value	Result
Arts	30	40.2	2.35	48	0.06	Not significant at 0.05 level
Science	20	41.4	1.84			

From the Table 2, it is observed that the obtained ‘t’ value 0.06 is lesser than the table value 2.01 at 0.05 level of significance with df 48. Hence the null hypothesis “There is no significant difference between Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers Teaching Performance” is accepted. This implies that both Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers are similar in their Teaching Performance.

Objective Three: To study the relationship between Pre-service Teachers Attitude towards Practice in Teaching and Teaching Performance

Ho 3: There is no significant relationship between Pre-service Teacher’s Attitude towards Practice in Teaching and Teaching Performance.

The objective was analysed and interpreted using Product Moment Correlation (r). The details of

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the test are given in the Table 3

Table 3: ‘r’ value of hypothesis

Variables	N	Table Value	Correlation ‘r’	Result
Attitude towards Practice in Teaching	50	0.27	0.37	Significant at 0.05
Teaching Performance	50			

From Table 3, it is observed that the obtained ‘r’ value 0.37 is greater than the theoretical value of 0.27 at 0.05 levels. Hence the null hypothesis ‘There is no significant correlation between Attitude towards Practice in Teaching and Teaching Performance of Pre-service Teachers’ is rejected. Thus, it can be concluded that there exists a significant positive correlation between Pre-service Teachers Attitude towards Practice in Teaching and Teaching Performance of Pre-service Teachers.

Major Findings of the Study

- There is no significant difference between Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers Attitude towards Practice in Teaching
- There is no significant difference between Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers Teaching Performance
- Significant positive correlation exists between Attitude towards Practice in Teaching and Teaching Performance of Pre-service Teachers

Educational Implications

- Practice Teaching is considered as essential requirement and valuable activity for the qualifications of a prospective teacher therefore it needs to be conducted effectively. Since Practice Teaching enables the student teachers to understand the problems and difficulties of teaching that they may face them in the future, student teachers need to be rigorously trained in various skills of teaching following a strict schedule.
- Teacher education colleges should give utmost importance for organizing the teaching practice in systematic way to develop their teaching performance and professional competencies. The teaching practice must be thoroughly monitored to ensure improved

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teaching performance. More time should be allotted so that can have rich teaching experience during the teaching practice.

- An orientation programme needs to be organized to train Pre-service Teachers in Practice Teaching. Seminars, conferences, workshops and discussions need to be conducted to orient Pre-service Teachers to their practice teaching and to train them in various teaching skills.
- An ample amount of pre-teaching experiences needs to be provided so that student teachers gain mastery over various skills of teaching. They should also be trained in the preparation of resources or teaching aids including charts, maps and so on.

Conclusion

Practice in Teaching is an integral part of initial teacher preparation programme which equips Pre-service Teachers with teaching skills, knowledge and competencies. A good teaching practice provides a best learning experience to the learners. The present study was undertaken, considering the importance of pre-service teachers teaching performance during practice in Teaching. Results showed that Arts and Science Pre-service Teachers were found to be similar in their Attitude towards Practice in Teaching and Teaching Performance. The study also revealed significant correlation between Perception towards Practice in Teaching and Teaching Performance. Thus, it can be concluded that a good teaching practice has great impact on fostering positive attitude among Pre-service Teachers.

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